

"UNDERSTANDING THE NEXUS: WORK ENVIRONMENT AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN ALBANIA"

MsC. Juna Muça

University of Tirana

Dr. Erjona Molla

University of Tirana

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10899650>

Abstract

This study explores the work environment and employee performance in Albania. It aims to test a model based on three dimensions of the work environment and their effect on employee performance. Data were collected from 115 employees of the Ministry of Justice and were processed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) to apply statistical tests, namely descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and regression analysis, to investigate the relationship of selected variables. The study results indicate that the majority of employees are males working at the managerial level. Pearson correlation results show that all independent variables have a strong and significant relationship with employee performance, especially job descriptions reflecting the strongest positive and significant relationship. Meanwhile, the regression analysis results indicate that employee performance is mostly influenced by training and development and communication practices. It was concluded that all three hypotheses were supported. Job descriptions have an impact on an individual's ability to work safely, competently, and in line with operational performance objectives. It is necessary to train employees to effectively and efficiently handle work overload. The current study suggests that improving job descriptions leads to better employee performance. This can result in improved organizational performance due to employee retention, and remaining employees strive to perform well in their positions.

Keywords: work environment, job descriptions, professional training, workplace performance

LITERATURE REVIEW

The work environment is paramount for various reasons. It directly impacts employee well-being, affecting their physical, mental, and emotional health. Every organization is required to monitor its internal and external environment for the attainment of specific goals. Organization is the structured entity established to attain specific objectives by blending of different types of resources (Ahmad, 2010)². A positive environment fosters higher levels of productivity, as employees feel more motivated and engaged in their tasks. Moreover, it significantly influences employee satisfaction and retention, as individuals are more likely to stay with organizations that prioritize their welfare. A conducive work environment also promotes innovation and creativity, as it encourages open communication, collaboration, and risk-taking. Additionally, ensuring a safe and healthy environment is not only a legal requirement but also a moral obligation, contributing to the overall reputation and brand image of the company. Ultimately, a supportive work environment is essential for nurturing teamwork, effective communication, and organizational success.

Having good job characteristics is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, job characteristics such as autonomy, variety, and opportunities for skill development contribute to employee satisfaction and motivation. When individuals feel a sense of control over their

work, engage in diverse tasks, and have chances to learn and grow professionally, they are more likely to be fulfilled and committed to their roles. Secondly, favorable job characteristics lead to higher levels of performance and productivity. The performance of public sector employees is affected by compensation practices and promotion practices whereas performance evaluation practices have insignificant impact on perceived employee performance (Bashir and Khattak 2008)³. Jobs that are challenging yet manageable, with clear goals and feedback mechanisms, enable employees to perform at their best. Additionally, positive job characteristics enhance employee well-being by reducing stress and burnout, as individuals experience a sense of accomplishment and fulfillment from their work. Brown et al. (2003) reported that a positive relationship between employees' perception of performance-related pay plans and management-employee relations.⁴ Overall, good job characteristics are essential for fostering employee engagement, performance, and well-being, ultimately benefiting both the individual and the organization.

The work environment is paramount for various reasons. It directly impacts employee well-being, affecting their physical, mental, and emotional health. Understand that the work environment can greatly affect employee morale (Kaczmarczyk, S et., 2002)⁵. A

² Ahmad A (2010). Application of Non-Financial Measures for Assessment of Performance of Islamic Banks in Pakistan, *Interdiscipl. J. Contemp. Res. Bus.*, 2 (7): 173-181

³ Bashir S, Khattak HR (2008). Impact of Selected HR Practices on Perceived Employee Performance, a Study of

Public Sector Employees in Pakistan. *Eur. J. Soc. Sci.*, 5(4): 243-252.

⁴ Brown S, Sessions JG (2003). Attitudes, Expectations, and Sharing. *Labour*, 17(4): 543-569.

⁵ Kaczmarczyk, S., Murtough, J., "Measuring the performance of innovative workplaces", *Journal of Facilities Management*, Vol. 1, 2002, pp.163-176

positive environment fosters higher levels of productivity, as employees feel more motivated and engaged in their tasks. Moreover, it significantly influences employee satisfaction and retention, as individuals are more likely to stay with organizations that prioritize their welfare. A conducive work environment also promotes innovation and creativity, as it encourages open communication, collaboration, and risk-taking. Additionally, ensuring a safe and healthy environment is not only a legal requirement but also a moral obligation, contributing to the overall reputation and brand image of the company. Ultimately, a supportive work environment is essential for nurturing teamwork, effective communication, and organizational success.

Having good job characteristics is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, job characteristics such as autonomy, variety, and opportunities for skill development contribute to employee satisfaction and motivation. When individuals feel a sense of control over their work, engage in diverse tasks, and have chances to learn and grow professionally, they are more likely to be fulfilled and committed to their roles. Secondly, favorable job characteristics lead to higher levels of performance and productivity. Jobs that are challenging yet manageable, with clear goals and feedback mechanisms, enable employees to perform at their best. Additionally, positive job characteristics enhance employee well-being by reducing stress and burnout, as individuals experience a sense of accomplishment and fulfillment from their work. Overall, good job characteristics are essential for fostering employee engagement, performance, and well-being, ultimately benefiting both the individual and the organization.

Training and development for employees are essential for several reasons. The training focuses on formal and systematic modification of behavior through learning which occurs as result of education, instruction, development and planned experience (Armstrong, 2000)⁶. Firstly, it enhances employees' skills and knowledge, enabling them to perform their roles more effectively and efficiently. This not only improves individual performance but also contributes to the overall success of the organization. Secondly, training and development foster employee engagement and motivation by demonstrating the organization's commitment to their growth and career advancement. When employees feel supported in their professional development, they are more likely to be loyal and invested in the organization. Additionally, training and development initiatives help to attract and retain top talent, as prospective employees are attracted to organizations that offer opportunities for learning and advancement. Ultimately, investing in training and development leads to a more skilled, engaged, and productive workforce, driving organizational success in the long run.

Communication practices are absolutely essential in a work environment for several reasons. Chen et al. (2006) found that there are positive relationships between organization communication, organizational commitment and job performance⁷. An effective communication fosters collaboration and teamwork among employees, enabling them to share ideas, coordinate tasks, and resolve conflicts efficiently. Clear and open communication also promotes transparency and trust within the organization, as employees feel informed and involved in decision-making processes. Moreover, communication practices facilitate alignment with organizational goals and objectives, ensuring that everyone understands their roles and responsibilities. Additionally, good communication enhances employee engagement and morale by providing feedback, recognition, and opportunities for dialogue. Effective interpersonal communication skills are essential for social interaction, building and maintenance of relationships. Poor communication skills can cause irrevocable damage to relationships; affecting productivity, satisfaction, performance, morale, trust, respect, self confidence and even physical health (Matin et al., 2010)⁸. Finally, effective communication with customers, clients, and other stakeholders is critical for building and maintaining positive relationships, which are vital for the success and reputation of the organization. In essence, communication practices form the foundation of a productive, collaborative, and harmonious work environment.

On the basis of existing literature, this study investigates the work environment and employee performance to test the following hypotheses:

H1: Job characteristics have a positive effect on the performance of employees

H2: Training and development have a positive effect on the performance of employees

H3: Communication practices have a positive effect on the performance of employees.

METHODOLOGY

The research work was a descriptive research of both primary data and secondary data. The research study is marked by prior formulation of research questions. This study investigates the influence of work environment (job characteristics, training and development and communication practices) and employee performance. The data was collected from the employees of Ministry of Justice by simple random sampling technique. It took two months to finalize the data collection and processing. The data was processed through SPSS to apply statistical tests, that is, descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation and regression analysis to investigate the relationship of the selected variables. The 250 questionnaires were distributed among employees working in Ministry of Justice, out of which 105 complete responses were received.

⁶ Armstrong M (2000). *Understanding training: Human Resource Management Practice*. (8th Ed). Kogan page limited, London

⁷ Chen J, Silverthorne C, Hung J (2006). Organization communication, job stress, organizational commitment and job performance of accounting professionals in Taiwan and America. *Leadersh. Organ. Dev. J.*, 27(4): 242-249.

⁸ Matin HZ, Jandaghi G, Karimi FH, Hamidzadeh A (2010). Relationship between Interpersonal Communication Skills and Organizational Commitment (Case Study: Jahad Keshavarzi and University of Qom, Iran). *Eur. J. Soc. Sci.*, 13(3): 387-398

The response rate of survey is 45.0%. Data was collected by structured questionnaire in English through personal contact approach by using a modified version of research instruments. The instrument of social support was adopted from Caplan et al. (1980)⁹. The items were assessed on a five point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree). The Cronbach alpha coefficient reveals $\alpha=0.71$ for this construct, indicating high reliability. Employees' perceptions of job characteristics conditions were recorded by Mohapatra and Srivastava (2003)¹⁰. It assessed the various aspect of job characteristics on five point Likert scale ranged from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree to inquire the working conditions. The alpha coefficient is $\alpha=0.79$, indicating high reliability. Similarly, the training and development of the employees was assessed by a local version of Chiang et al. (2005)¹¹. Items are rated on a five point Likert scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree. The coefficient of alpha is $\alpha=0.71$, depicts good reliability. Similarly, communication practices were documented by Penley and Hawkins (1985)¹². Items are

rated along a five point Likert scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly. Finally, the employees' performance was measured by a modified version of Babin and Boles (1998)¹³.

Items were rated on a five point Likert scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly and the alpha coefficient $\alpha=0.81$ indicates the reasonable reliability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study investigates the effect of work environment on performance of the employees. The data was collected and processed through SPSS to apply statistical tests, that is, descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation and regression analysis to investigate the relationship of the selected variables. Demographic profile indicates that majority of respondents age is between 26 to 40 years. 76% of the respondents are female while 24% represents the male segment. Employees were classified on the basis of the designation and reveals that 40% of the total respondents consist of civil servant, 35% head of department and rest of the lot that is 25% represents by directors.

Tab.1

Summary of Pearson's correlation between selected variables

Variable	Pearson correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Job Characteristics and Employee Performance	0.861**	0.000
Training and Development and Employee Performance	0.838**	0.000
Communication Process and Employee Performance	0.879**	0.000

**Significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 1 reflects the results of Pearson's correlation for the selected variables. It shows that all the independent variables such as social support, physical working conditions, job characteristics, training and development and communication practices have a strong and significant relationship with employee performance.

Table 2 reflects the regression coefficients for the selected variables. The results of multiple regression analysis confirmed the relationship between the dependent variable (employee performance) and the inde-

pendent variables (job characteristics, training and development and communication practices). The results show that job characteristics ($\beta=0.293$) has weak non-significant positive influence on the employee performance, training and development ($\beta=0.611$) reflects the strong positive and significant impact on performance. Finally, communication practices ($\beta=0.590$) indicates the strong positive and significant relationship with employee performance. The results supported the hypothesis as it is evident that there is positive relationship between the selected variables.

Tab. 2.

Summary of the work environment and employee performance-regression model (coefficients, standard error in parenthesis, t- values in brackets and p-values in italics). Dependent variable: EP, Employee performance. Independent variables: JC, job characteristics; TD, training and development; CP, communication practices.

Constant	JC	TD	CP	R2	F- statistic
24.215 (0.329) [0.305] 0.000	0.283 (0.135) [3.682] 0.483	0.601 (0.181) [3.201] 0.000	0.580 (0.113) [4.216] 0.002	0.859	144.430 0.000

⁹ Caplan RD, Cobb S, French Jr. JRP, Harrison RV, Pinneau Jr. SR (1980). Job demands and Worker Health. Main Effects and Occupational Differences, The Institute for Social Research: University of Michigan.

¹⁰ Mohapatra BK, Srivastava AK (2003). A study of the relationship of perceived work environment with job attitude, performance and health. unpublished PhD. Dissertation, Department of Psychology, Banaras Hindu University

¹¹ Chiang CF, Back KJ, Canter D (2005). The Impact of Employee Training on Job Satisfaction and Intention to Stay

in the Hotel Industry, J. Hum. Res. Hosp. Tourism, 4(2): 99 - 118.

¹² Penley LE, Hawkins B (1985). Studying interpersonal communication in organizations: a leadership application. Acad. Manage. J., 28(2): 309- 326.

¹³ Babin J, Boles J (1998). Employee Behavior in a Service Environment: A Model and Test of Potential Differences between Men and Women, J. Mark., 62: 77 - 91.

Table 2 indicates that R^2 is 0.859 and F-statistic is 144.430. It confirms the fitness of the model. The R^2 shows that independent variables such as job characteristics, training and development and communication practices account for 86.9% variation in the dependent variable that is performance of employees. The findings reveal that all the hypotheses are upheld. First hypothesis is accepted as positive effect of job characteristics on employee performance. Similarly, the second hypothesis proves true in the existence of positive relationship between training and development and performance of employees. Lastly, the results also reveal a positive relationship between communication practices and performance of employees.

It is concluded that performance of employees mostly depends upon work environment (training and development and communication practices). The results of the study support the findings of the earlier researches that employee performance is affected by the factors such as job characteristics, training and development, and communication practices are integral components of a thriving work environment. Job characteristics that provide autonomy, variety, and opportunities for growth not only enhance employee satisfaction and motivation but also drive performance and well-being. Likewise, investing in training and development programs demonstrates a commitment to employee growth, leading to a more skilled and engaged workforce. Moreover, effective communication practices foster collaboration, transparency, and alignment with organizational goals, promoting a culture of trust and teamwork. Together, these elements contribute to a positive work environment where employees feel valued, supported, and empowered to succeed, ultimately benefiting both individuals and the organization as a whole.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

Work environment is an important element in the organizational studies. This study investigates the work environment and employee performance in Albania. The study aims to test a model based on three dimensions of work environment and their effect on the performance of employees. The data was collected from 105 employees of Ministry of Justice and processed through SPSS to apply statistical tests that is, descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation and regression analysis to investigate the relationship of the selected variables. The results reveal that most of the employees are male and working at the supervisory level. The Pearson's correlation results show positive relationship between dimensions of work environment and employee performance. Whereas, the results of multiple regression analysis reveal that employee performance mostly depends upon training, development and communication practices. It is concluded that the entire hypotheses are upheld.

It is necessary to train the employees to efficiently and effectively handle the work overload. The aim behind training of employees is "achieving cost effective high performance" that leads to quality assurance. Effective communication practices have a positive effect

on employee performance. The finding suggests that institutions should strengthen their communication channels and processes in order to enhance the employee's job performance. The current study suggests that improvement in the working conditions leads to better employees' performance. It could result into improved performance of the organization due to retention of employees and the retained employees try their best to perform well at their work places.

References:

- Ahmad A (2010). Application of Non-Financial Measures for Assessment of Performance of Islamic Banks in Pakistan, *Interdiscipl. J. Contemp. Res. Bus.*, 2 (7): 173-181
- Armstrong M (2000). *Understanding training: Human Resource Management Practice*. (8th Ed). Kogan page limited, London
- Babin J, Boles J (1998). Employee Behavior in a Service Environment: A Model and Test of Potential Differences between Men and Women, *J. Mark.*, 62: 77 – 91.
- Bashir S, Khattak HR (2008). Impact of Selected HR Practices on Perceived Employee Performance, a Study of Public Sector Employees in Pakistan. *Eur. J. Soc. Sci.*, 5(4): 243-252.
- Brown S, Sessions JG (2003). Attitudes, Expectations, and Sharing, *Labour*, 17(4): 543-569.
- Caplan RD, Cobb S, French Jr. JRP, Harrison RV, Pinneau Jr. SR (1980). *Job demands and Worker Health. Main Effects and Occupational Differences*, The Institute for Social Research: University of Michigan.
- Chen J, Silverthorne C, Hung J (2006). Organization communication, job stress, organizational commitment and job performance of accounting professionals in Taiwan and America. *Leadersh. Organ. Dev. J.*, 27(4): 242-249.
- Chiang CF, Back KJ, Canter D (2005). The Impact of Employee Training on Job Satisfaction and Intention to Stay in the Hotel Industry, *J. Hum. Res. Hosp. Tourism*, 4(2): 99 -118.
- Kaczmarczyk S, Murtough, J., "Measuring the performance of innovative workplaces", *Journal of Facilities Management*, Vol. 1, 2002, pp.163-176
- Matin HZ, Jandaghi G, Karimi FH, Hamidzadeh A (2010). Relationship between Interpersonal Communication Skills and Organizational Commitment (Case Study: Jahad Keshavarzi and University of Qom, Iran). *Eur. J. Soc. Sci.*, 13(3): 387-398
- Mohapatra BK, Srivastava AK (2003). A study of the relationship of perceived work environment with job attitude, performance and health. unpublished PhD. Dissertation, Department of Psychology, Banaras Hindu University
- Penley LE, Hawkins B (1985). Studying interpersonal communication in organizations: a leadership application. *Acad. Manage. J.*, 28(2): 309-326.